

MIXED-MODE GROWTH OF INTERLAMINAR CRACKS IN CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Mixed-mode propagation behavior of interlaminar fatigue cracks was studied with unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates, Toray T800H/#3631. Mixed-mode fatigue tests were conducted by the mixed mode bending method under the mixed-mode ratio, K_I/K_{II} , of 0.10 and 0.68, and the cyclic stress ratio, R , of 0.2 and 0.5. Both the mode I and mode II stress intensity factors affect the crack propagation rate. For the mode II-dominant crack propagation, the propagation rate was sensitive to the K_I -component, while for the mode I-dominant propagation, there was no significant acceleration of the crack growth by superimposing a small amount of the K_{II} -component.

INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar fracture, or delamination, commonly occurs in highly loaded composite laminate structures. To establish the damage tolerance and durability design criteria for composite structures, the complete characterization of propagation behavior of interlaminar fatigue cracks is required. Most of the previous works have been concerned with the crack propagation under pure mode I (opening) and pure mode II (shear) cyclic loadings. Less attention has been devoted to the mixed-mode propagation of interlaminar fatigue cracks.

In the present paper, the mixed mode I/II propagation behavior of interlaminar fatigue cracks was investigated with unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates. The mixed mode bending (MMB) method was used for mixed-mode fatigue tests. The effects of the cyclic stress ratio and the mixed-mode ratio on the fatigue crack propagation were discussed on the basis of the experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

The unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates, T800H/#3631, made from preregs supplied

Table 1. Mechanical properties of material.

Prepreg		Toray P2212-15
Carbon fiber		T800H
Epoxy resin		#3631
Cure temperature		180°C
Fiber volume fraction		60.3 %
Constitution of laminate		(0) ₄₄
Elastic constants	E_1 (GPa)	137
	E_2 (GPa)	8.1
	G_{12} (GPa)	4.8
	ν_{12}	0.31
	ν_{23}	0.55
Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness,	K_{Ic} (MPa \sqrt{m})	1.4
Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness,	K_{IIc} (MPa \sqrt{m})	6.2

by Toray Inc. were used in the present study. A nominal thickness of the laminates is 6.2 mm (44 plies). A Kapton film of 12 μm in thickness was inserted as a delamination starter at the mid-plane of the laminate.

Table 1 summarizes the mechanical properties of the unidirectional laminates. The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , was measured by using the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens and represents the value at the onset of a crack from a starter film. The value of the mode I fracture toughness increased with crack extension because of the development of fiber bridging. On the other hand, the mode II fracture toughness, K_{IIc} , determined by the end-notched flexure (ENF) and the end-loaded split (ELS) methods was fairly constant during crack growth.

Split laminate beam specimens were cut from these laminates, and have a width, B , of 20

Figure 1. Mixed mode bending test.

mm and a height, $2h$, of 6.2 mm.

MIXED MODE BENDING TEST

Figure 1 illustrates the MMB test method proposed by Reeder and Crews [1-3]. Mode I and mode II loadings are simultaneously applied to a split beam specimen by means of an F-shaped loading lever. The upward load at the end of the lever produces mode I loading similar to the DCB test. The downward load at the fulcrum of the lever creates mode II loading similar to the ENF test. The ratio of mode I to mode II loading can be varied by changing the length between the load point on the lever and the fulcrum, c , as follows:

$$P_I/P_{II} = 3/4 - 1/(1 + c/L) \quad (1)$$

where L is the half-span length (50 mm). The value of P_I/P_{II} increases with increasing the c/L value.

STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR

Linear Analysis

The linear analysis of the mode I and mode II stress intensity factors of the MMB test specimen was conducted by the boundary element method (BEM). The special Green's function for an infinite anisotropic plate containing a straight crack given by Snyder and Cruse [4] was used in the present analysis. The values of the stress intensity factors, K_{IBEM} and K_{IIBEM} , obtained by BEM are well approximated by the following functions of the crack length, a , and the loading position, c/L :

$$K_{IBEM} = \left\{ \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{3c}{L} - 1 \right) \left(3.07 \frac{a}{2h} + 2.87 \right) - \left(1 + \frac{c}{L} \right) f \left(\frac{a}{2h} \right) \right\} \frac{P}{B\sqrt{2h}} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{IIBEM} = \left(1 + \frac{c}{L} \right) \left(1.24 \frac{a}{2h} + 0.448 \right) \frac{P}{B\sqrt{2h}} \quad (3)$$

$$f(\xi) = 0.044(1 - 0.1\xi + 0.095\xi^2 - 0.01\xi^3) \quad (4)$$

where P is the load applied to the loading lever, B is the specimen width and $2h$ is the specimen height.

Nonlinear Effect

The geometric nonlinearity appears in the load-displacement relation of the MMB test. This nonlinearity is caused by the rotation of the loading lever. The effect of the nonlinearity on the stress intensity factors is analyzed on the basis of the modified beam theory proposed by Reeder and Crews [2, 3]. The values of the stress intensity factors given by Eqs. (2)~(4) should be corrected as follows:

$$K_I = K_{IBEM} F_{Int} \quad (5)$$

$$K_{II} = K_{IIBEM} F_{Int} \quad (6)$$

The mode I correction factor, F_{Int} , obtained by the nonlinear analysis depends on the

applied load P , the crack length a , and the loading position c/L , and takes a value between 0.90 and 1.08, while the mode II correction factor, $F_{II\epsilon}$, is between 0.90 and 1.00.

The range of the stress intensity factor is defined by

$$\Delta K_i = K_{imax} - K_{imin} \quad (i = I, II) \quad (7)$$

where K_{imax} and K_{imin} are the mode i stress intensity factors corresponding to the maximum and minimum loads, respectively.

FATIGUE TESTING

Fatigue tests were conducted with a servo-hydraulic fatigue testing machine in air at room temperature. The frequency of stress cycling was 10 Hz. The pure mode I and mode II propagation behavior of interlaminar fatigue cracks were examined by the DCB and ENF tests, respectively. The mixed-mode fatigue tests were conducted by the MMB method. The mixed-mode ratio, K_I/K_{II} , was 0.10 ($c/L = 0.40$) and 0.68 ($c/L = 0.90$). For each mixed-mode ratio, the fatigue tests were carried out under the stress ratio, R , of 0.2 and 0.5.

For the pure mode I tests, the crack propagation rate was determined under the ΔK -constant conditions. The crack length was measured by the compliance method [5]. On the other hand, for the pure mode II and the mixed-mode tests, the propagation rate was examined under the ΔK -decreasing and the ΔK -increasing conditions. The crack length was measured with a travelling microscope at a magnification of 200. White marking ink was painted on the specimen surfaces to detect the crack tip clearly.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EFFECT OF STRESS RATIO

Figure 2 (a)~(d) shows the relation between the crack propagation rate, da/dN , and the stress intensity range, ΔK , for each mixed-mode ratio. In Fig. 2 (d), the propagation rate of the pure mode I cracks is plotted against the local crack-tip stress intensity range, $\Delta K_{I\text{tip}}$, defined by the following equation [6]:

$$\Delta K_{I\text{tip}} = \Delta K_{Iap} - \Delta K_{I\text{bridge}} \quad (8)$$

where ΔK_{Iap} is the stress intensity range by the applied load, and $\Delta K_{I\text{bridge}}$ is the shielding stress intensity range due to fiber bridging. For the pure mode II and the mixed-mode cracks, the effect of the fiber bridging on the crack propagation rate was minimal.

For each stress ratio, the crack propagation rate is given by a power function of ΔK or K_{max} in the region of rates above 10^{-9} m/cycle. The exponent of the power function n at $R = 0.5$ is larger than that at $R = 0.2$ for all the cases of the mixed-mode ratio examined. Below $da/dN = 10^{-9}$ m/cycle, the propagation rate is lower than that given by the power function. There is a threshold value of ΔK (or K_{max}) for the fatigue crack propagation.

For each mixed-mode ratio, the crack propagation rate is higher for larger R value when

Figure 2. Effect of stress ratio on relation between crack propagation rate and stress intensity range.

compared at the same ΔK value, because the K_{max} value affects the propagation rate as well as ΔK . The contribution of K_{max} on the propagation rate is larger at the higher rates, while the effect of ΔK increases as the rate decreases. In particular, for the case of the mode II-dominant condition such as pure mode II or $K_I/K_{II} = 0.10$, the near-threshold propagation is controlled only by the ΔK value, and independent of the K_{max} value.

EFFECT OF MIXED-MODE RATIO

The crack propagation rate for $R = 0.2$ is plotted against the mode I stress intensity range ΔK_I in Fig. 3. When compared at the same value of ΔK_I , the crack propagation rate increases with increasing the K_{II} -component of loading. The figures associated with the fitting lines in Fig. 3 indicate the exponent of the power relation between da/dN and ΔK_I . The exponent is smaller for the smaller values of K_I/K_{II} .

Figure 3. Relation between crack propagation rate and mode I stress intensity range.

Figure 4. Relation between crack propagation rate and mode II stress intensity range.

The same data of da/dN are plotted against the mode II stress intensity range ΔK_{II} in Fig. 4. The propagation rate at the same ΔK_{II} value increases as the K_I -component increases. Both mode I and mode II loadings affect the crack propagation rate as seen in Figs. 3 and 4. The similar results was obtained for $R = 0.5$.

The condition of the mixed-mode fatigue crack propagation on the $K_{I_{max}} - K_{II_{max}}$ plane is shown in Fig. 5. The solid symbols indicate the condition of the mixed-mode interlaminar fracture under static loading. In the region of the mode I-dominant fatigue crack propa-

(a) $R=0.2$

(b) $R=0.5$

Figure 5. Condition of mixed-mode fatigue crack propagation.

gation, the $K_{I_{max}}$ value is nearly constant at a constant propagation rate. It is concluded that the propagation rate is controlled by $K_{I_{max}}$ and ΔK_I , and nearly independent of the mode II stress intensity factor for the mode I-dominant propagation. On the other hand, in the region of the mode II-dominant propagation, there is the $K_I - K_{II}$ interaction on the crack propagation rate; the propagation rate is sensitive to the K_I value as well as the K_{II} value. The $K_I - K_{II}$ relation at a constant propagation rate is very similar to that for the static fracture condition. However, for the $K_I - K_{II}$ relation at $da/dN = 10^{-9}$ m/cycle, the $K_{I_{max}}$ value in the mode I-dominant region is slightly reduced by superimposing a small amount of mode II loading. This suggests that the K_{II} -component affects the near-threshold propagation under mode I-dominant loading.

CONCLUSIONS

1. For each mixed-mode ratio and stress ratio, the crack propagation rate was given by a power function of the stress intensity range ΔK or the maximum stress intensity factor K_{max} in the region of rates above 10^{-9} m/cycle. Below this region, there exists a threshold stress intensity factor for the fatigue crack propagation.
2. For all the mixed-mode ratio examined, the crack propagation rate was affected by both the ΔK and K_{max} values. The effect of ΔK on the propagation rate increased with decreasing the propagation rate and the mixed-mode ratio K_I/K_{II} .
3. For the mode I-dominant propagation, the propagation rate was nearly independent of the mode II stress intensity factor and controlled by the ΔK_I and $K_{I_{max}}$ values, while for the mode II-dominant propagation, there was the $K_I - K_{II}$ interaction on the fatigue crack propagation.

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